

Coagulation of Gelatin Sols in Alcohol-Water Mixture.

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It is well-known that isoelectric gelatin can be coagulated by alcohol. Fenn (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1918, **33**, 270) found that the presence of acids, alkalis and salts hinders the precipitation of gelatin by alcohol. It is interesting to note from the results of Loeb ("Proteins and the Theory of Colloidal Behaviour," 1922, p. 252) that with acidified gelatin, which behaves like a positively charged colloid, far greater amounts of electrolytes with polyvalent cations (*e.g.* CaCl_2 , BaCl_2 , AlCl_3 etc.) are required than NaCl , KCl , etc., in spite of the fact that for positively charged sols only chloride ions are potent in coagulating the sols. Polyvalent cations possess an inhibiting action on the precipitation of acidified gelatin in alcohol-water mixture. Similarly, with alkaline gelatin, which behaves like a negatively charged sol, polyvalent anions from electrolytes like Na_2SO_4 , $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $\text{Na}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, etc., also possess an inhibiting action on its precipitation. These results of Loeb seem to indicate that the valency of the ions carrying a charge similar to that on the colloid particles is an important factor in the coagulation of gelatin in alcohol-water mixture.

In previous publications (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 435, 659; 1927, **31**, 187; *Kolloid Z.*, 1924, **34**, 262; 1925, **36**, 131) we have shown that the sols which are capable of adsorbing appreciable amounts of the similarly charged ion from the precipitating electrolyte require larger quantities of the electrolyte for precipitation. We have also proved that these sols show abnormal dilution effect, *viz.* greater amounts of an electrolyte are necessary for coagulation of diluted sols than concentrated ones, develop 'ionic antagonism' when coagulated by mixtures of electrolytes and show the phenomenon of positive acclimatization.

In order to throw light on the nature of gelatin we have investigated (a) the influence of dilution of the gelatin sol in alcohol-water on its coagulation, and (b) precipitation with mixtures of electrolytes, and (c) the phenomenon of acclimatization.

Positively charged gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture.—Purified gelatin (Goldruck, Kahlbaum) containing 0.1% ash and p_H value 5.8 was used. Five gm. of gelatin were dissolved at 80° in 50 c.c. of water, and 12.5 c.c. $N/8$ -HCl were added and the total volume was made up to 500 c.c. with absolute alcohol. The p_H value of aqueous gelatin of the same concentration in presence of 12.5 c.c. $N/8$ -HCl was also determined and found to be 4.4.

The opalescent gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture was sensitive to electrolytes and it was found that water has a remarkable stabilising influence. 4 C.c. of the gelatin sol and 0.5 c.c. of the coagulating electrolytes were separately taken and then mixed up and left for half an hour when the coagulation was observed.

Influence of dilution on the coagulation of positively charged gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture.

The sol is diluted with 87.5% alcohol which is the amount present in the original sol (Sol A).

TABLE I.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate in c.c.		
	Sol A.	Sol A/2.	Sol A/3.
KCl $N/10$	0.26	0.43	>0.50
K_2SO_4 $N/50$	0.25	0.22	0.18
$K_3Fe(CN)_6$ $N/100$	0.42	0.36	0.30
HCl $N/25$	0.35	>0.50	—
$MgCl_2$ $N/2.5$	0.26	0.48	—

The above table shows that the sol becomes stable on dilution when coagulated by KCl, HCl and $MgCl_2$. The sol could not be coagulated by $Al(NO_3)_3$ and the opalescence disappears when the electrolyte is added to the sol. Barium chloride also behaves like $Al(NO_3)_3$ and the sol could be coagulated only by a saturated solution of $BaCl_2$. Smaller concentrations of HCl and $MgCl_2$ also make the sol clear.

TABLE II.

Coagulation with a mixture of KCl and K₂SO₄.

Amount of N/10 -KCl added in c.c.	Amount of N/50-K ₂ SO ₄ required for coagulation in c.c.		
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.
0.26	0	—	—
0	0.26	—	—
0.05	0.24	0.20	+0.04
0.10	0.21	0.16	+0.05
0.15	0.17	0.11	+0.06

TABLE III.

Coagulation with a mixture of MgCl₂ and K₂SO₄.

Amount of N/20-MgCl ₂ to coagulate in c.c.	Amount of N/50-K ₂ SO ₄ required for coagulation in c.c.		
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.
0.26	0	—	—
0	0.26	—	—
0.05	0.26	0.20	+0.06
0.10	0.24	0.16	+0.08
0.15	0.22	0.11	+0.11

TABLE IV.

Coagulation with a mixture of BaCl₂ and KCl.

BaCl ₂ N/20 added in c.c.	...	0	0.05	0.10
Amount of N/10-KCl required for coagulation in c.c.	...	0.26	0.30	0.38

TABLE V.

Coagulation with a mixture of HCl and KCl.

N/2.5-HCl added in c.c.	Amount of N/10-KCl to coagulate in c.c.		
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.
0	0.26	—	—
0.35	0	—	—
0.05	0.28	0.22	+0.06
0.10	0.27	0.19	+0.08

TABLE VI.

Coagulation with a mixture of HCl and K₂SO₄.

<i>N/25</i> -HCl added in c.c.	Amount of <i>N/50</i> -K ₂ SO ₄ required to coagulate in c.c. Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.
0	0·25	—	—
0·35	0	—	—
0·05	0·28	0·21	+0·07
0·10	0·28	0·18	+0·10

TABLE VII.

Coagulation with a mixture of Al(NO₃)₃ and KCl.

<i>N/20</i> -Al(NO ₃) ₃ added in c.c.	... 0	0·05	0·10
Amount of KCl to coagulate in c.c.	... 0·26 of <i>N/10</i>	0·33 of <i>N/10</i> .	0·22 of <i>N/5</i> .

The results recorded in Tables II, III, V and VI show that the phenomenon of 'ionic antagonism' appears when gelatin in alcohol-water mixture is coagulated with KCl+K₂SO₄, MgCl₂+K₂SO₄, HCl+K₂SO₄, and HCl+KCl. The sol is remarkably stabilised in presence of BaCl₂ and Al(NO₃)₃ when coagulated by KCl.

In order to investigate the phenomenon of acclimatization by an electrolyte, 4 c.c. of the sol were treated with 0·04 c.c. of the electrolyte at a time after every fifteen minutes till coagulation was observed. The coagulation was investigated one hour after the last addition of electrolyte. The amount necessary to coagulate the sol, when the electrolyte was added all at once, is determined by pouring the whole of the required electrolyte to 4 c.c. of the sol and the coagulation was observed after one hour. The following results were obtained.

TABLE VIII.

Electrolyte.	Amount required to coagulate when added slowly in c.c. (0·4 c.c. at a time).	Amount to coagulate when added all at once in c.c.
KCl <i>N/20</i>	0·36	0·30
HCl <i>N/25</i>	0·28	0·20
MgCl ₂ <i>N/5</i>	0·38	0·30
K ₂ SO ₄ <i>N/100</i>	0·28	0·30

The results in the foregoing table show that appreciable amount of positive acclimatization is developed when the sol is coagulated by KCl, HCl and MgCl₂. Very slight negative acclimatization is developed with K₂SO₄.

Negatively charged gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture.—0.5 Gm. of gelatin was dissolved in 5 c.c. of water at 80° and 2.5 c.c. of N/10-KOH. The solution is made up to 500 c.c. with absolute alcohol. The p_H value of 0.1 % gelatin solution in presence of 2.5 c.c. of N/10-KOH is found to be 7.90. The gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture is opalescent. The following results were obtained on the coagulation of the sols of different concentrations.

Influence of dilution on the coagulation of negatively charged sol in alcohol-water mixture.

TABLE IX.

The sol is diluted with the same percentage of alcohol-water mixture as present in the original sol.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate in c.c.		
	Sol A.	Sol A/2.	Sol A/3.
KCl N/10	0.32	0.28	0.26
K ₂ SO ₄ N/5	0.30	0.32	0.35
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ N/5	0.24	0.25	0.25
BaCl ₂ N/100	0.30	0.18	0.15
MgCl ₂ N/50	0.25	0.18	0.15
KOH N/3.5	0.22	0.30	0.36
HCl N/50	0.26	0.20	0.15
Al(NO ₃) ₃ N/100	0.25	0.20	0.15

The above results show that the sol behaves abnormally towards dilution when coagulated by K₂SO₄, K₄Fe(CN)₆ and KOH; on the other hand, it behaves normally towards dilution when coagulated by KCl, BaCl₂, MgCl₂ and HCl. When amounts of Al(NO₃)₃ or HCl slightly greater than the precipitating concentrations are added to the sol, it becomes clear and charge reversal is observed. Amounts of KOH smaller than the precipitating concentration also make the sol clear.

TABLE X.

Coagulation with a mixture of KCl and BaCl₂.

Amount of N/10-KCl added in c.c.	Amount of BaCl ₂ to coagulate in c.c.		
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.
0	0.30	—	—
0.32	0	—	—
0.05	0.24	0.25	-0.01
0.10	0.18	0.20	-0.02

There is no ' ionic antagonism ' when the sol is coagulated with mixtures of KCl and BaCl₂.

TABLE XI.

Coagulation with mixtures of K₂SO₄ and MgCl₂.

Amount of N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ added in c.c.	Amount of N/50-MgCl ₂ to coagulate in c.c.		
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.
0	0.25	—	—
0.30	0	—	—
0.05	0.21	0.21	0
0.10	0.18	0.17	+0.01
0.15	0.15	0.13	+0.02

Very slight ' ionic antagonism ' is observed when the sol is coagulated with a mixture of K₂SO₄ and MgCl₂.

TABLE XII.

Coagulation with mixtures of KOH and KCl.

Amount of N/15-KOH added in c.c.	...	0	0.05	0.10
Amount of N/10-KCl to coagulate in c.c.	...	0.32	0.35	0.40

The foregoing results show that the sol is appreciably stabilised towards its coagulation by KCl in presence of KOH.

Experiments on the phenomenon of acclimatization were made with the negatively charged sol as was done with the positively charged sol. The following results were obtained.

TABLE XIII.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate when added slowly in c.c. (0.04 c.c. at a time).	Amount to coagulate when added all at once in c.c.
KCl N/10	0.24	0.25
K ₂ SO ₄ N/10	0.28	0.25
BaCl ₂ N/200	0.32	0.40
MgCl ₂ N/100	0.28	0.35
KOH N/35	0.24	0.15
HCl N/100	0.16	0.20
Al(NO ₃) ₃ N/200	0.20	0.30

From the above table it will be seen that the phenomenon of positive acclimatization is slightly developed when the sol is coagulated by K₂SO₄ whilst considerable amount of negative acclimatization is developed when the sol is coagulated by BaCl₂, MgCl₂, HCl and Al(NO₃)₃. The phenomenon of positive acclimatization is, however, developed with KOH.

Discussion.

Our experimental results with a positively charged sol of gelatin show that it could not be coagulated by BaCl₂ and Al(NO₃)₃ and these electrolytes also exert remarkable antagonistic action towards the coagulation of the sol by KCl. The amounts of HCl and MgCl₂ required to coagulate the sol are greater than that of KCl and small concentrations of these electrolytes stabilise the sol, and antagonistic action is developed when the sol is coagulated by mixtures of K₂SO₄ + MgCl₂, HCl + KCl, and HCl + K₂SO₄. Slight 'ionic antagonism' is also observed when the sol is coagulated with mixtures of KCl and K₂SO₄. The sol becomes stable on dilution when coagulated by KCl, MgCl₂ and HCl. It is also observed that KCl, MgCl₂ and HCl develop the phenomenon of positive acclimatization with the positively charged sol of gelatin in alcohol-water mixture.

In previous publications we have shown that if an ion carrying the same charge as the colloid particle is absorbed by the sol from an electrolyte the following should result:—

(i) Adsorption of the similarly charged ions would increase the charge on the colloid particles and consequently inhibit the action of the oppositely charged ion, which causes coagulation.

(ii) The ratio of the amounts of adsorption of the similarly charged ions to that of oppositely charged ions increases with the dilution of the sol, and this results in the stability of the sol on dilution towards its coagulation by the electrolyte.

(iii) The percentage of adsorption of similarly charged ions is greater from a dilute solution than from a concentrated one. This causes 'ionic antagonism' and the phenomenon of positive acclimatization.

It appears, therefore, from Tables I-VIII that a sol of acidified gelatin in alcohol-water mixture can adsorb K° , $Ba^{\circ\circ}$, $Mg^{\circ\circ}$, H° and $Al^{\circ\circ\circ}$ ions.

From the results of Loeb on the coagulation of negatively charged sol of gelatin in alcohol-water mixture, it will be found that the amounts of K_2SO_4 , K_3 -citrate, $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, etc., necessary for coagulation are greater than that of KCl . This points to the conclusion that anions, $SO_4^{''}$, $Fe(CN)_6^{''''}$ and Citrate $'''$ are adsorbed in greater amounts than Cl' , when the amount adsorbed is expressed in equivalent. Our results on the coagulation of the negatively charged sol with mixtures of KCl and $BaCl_2$ show that no ionic antagonism is developed, and the sol behaves normally towards dilution when coagulated by these electrolytes separately. On the other hand, slight 'ionic antagonism' is developed when the sol is coagulated with mixtures of K_2SO_4 and $MgCl_2$, showing that $SO_4^{''}$ ions possess an inhibiting action on the coagulation of the sol. The sol also becomes stable on dilution when coagulated by K_2SO_4 . Considerable amount of 'ionic antagonism' is developed when the sol is coagulated with mixtures of KOH and KCl . The sol behaves abnormally on dilution when coagulated by KOH . The phenomenon of acclimatization studied with the negatively charged sol of gelatin in alcohol-water mixture show that whilst positive acclimatization is observed with K_2SO_4 and KOH , slight negative acclimatization is observed with KCl and it is more pronounced with $BaCl_2$, $MgCl_2$, HCl and $Al(NO_3)_3$. In papers published from these laboratories (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 659; 1927, 31, 649; *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 37, 141; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 313) we have shown that when a sol can adsorb the oppositely charged ions in large amounts, so that the adsorption of the similarly charged ions is comparatively small, the phenomenon of negative acclimatization is developed. We are, therefore, of opinion that a negatively charged sol of gelatin can adsorb appreciable

amounts of anions like $\text{SO}_4^{''}$, citrate,^{'''} OH' , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{'''}$ from K_2SO_4 , K_3 -citrate, KOH and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, but the amount of adsorption of anions from KCl , MgCl_2 , $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, BaCl_2 and HCl is not at all significant in comparison with the amount of adsorption of cations from these electrolytes.

Gelatin, being an amino acid, can behave both as an acid and a base, and therefore, can adsorb both cations and anions. We have, however, shown in this paper that gelatin prefers to take up a cation more easily than an anion. Thus we have shown in this paper that gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture can adsorb appreciable amounts of cations like $\text{Ba}^{\circ\circ}$, $\text{Al}^{\circ\circ}$, $\text{Mg}^{\circ\circ}$, etc., whether it is charged positively or negatively, because the acidic character of gelatin is more pronounced than the basic and it exerts an affinity for the adsorption of cations. We have also observed that polyvalent cations are required in very large amounts to coagulate a positively charged sol of gelatin and can very easily bring charge reversal of the negatively charged sols, whilst polyvalent anions cannot bring about charge reversal of the positively charged sol. This is because gelatin can take up more cations than anions. It is well known that the p_H value of the isoelectric gelatin is 4.70 and that gelatin begins to behave as a base, when the medium is distinctly acidic. This also indicates that gelatin possesses greater acidic properties than basic, and is therefore capable of adsorbing comparatively larger amounts of cations than anions.

From Fenn's results it will be seen that polyvalent cations possess a stabilising influence for the positively charged sol and the polyvalent anions have a stabilising effect on the negatively charged sol of gelatin in alcohol-water mixture. Loeb has shown that isoelectric gelatin is more easily dissolved in an electrolyte containing either a polyvalent cation or a polyvalent anion. We are of opinion that these observations of Fenn and Loeb originate from the property of gelatin which can adsorb both polyvalent cations and anions.

Perrin (*J. Chim. phys.*, 1904, 2, 601; 1905, 3, 50) has observed that salts with trivalent cations can reverse the charge of negatively charged membranes and that tetravalent anions cause the reversal of charge of positively charged membranes. Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1921-22, 4, 463) has found that LaCl_3 and CeCl_3 or $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ makes a film of isoelectric gelatin to assume an electric charge either positive or negative due to the adsorption of $\text{La}^{\circ\circ\circ}$ and $\text{Ce}^{\circ\circ\circ}$ ions or $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{'''}$ ion.

Our experimental results on the coagulation of gelatin sol in presence of either alkali or acid in alcohol-water mixture show that the negatively charged sol can adsorb anions like SO_4^{--} , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{--}$, OH' , etc., and the positively charged sol can adsorb cations like Ba° , $\text{Al}^{\circ\circ}$, H° , etc. Loeb, however, believes that only cations can be taken up by gelatin containing alkali and that only anions can be adsorbed by gelatin containing acid. On the other hand, Pauli (*Fortschr. naturwiss. Forschung*, 1912, 4, 223) holds that both ions of a salt are adsorbed by a protein.

Loeb considers that the effect of ions like $\text{Ca}^{\circ\circ}$, $\text{La}^{\circ\circ\circ}$, etc., in inhibiting the precipitation of positively charged gelation sol in alcohol-water arises from the increasing effect of these ions on the forces of attraction between water and gelatin. It is generally believed that great hydration is associated with marked stability of the sol. In previous papers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 149; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 303) we have shown that hydration of sols need not be a significant factor for the stability of sols. Loeb ("Proteins and the Theory of Colloidal Behaviour," 1922, p. 91) has shown that the viscosity of gelatin sol is markedly decreased in presence of neutral salts and this shows that the degree of hydration of the sol is decreased by the addition of electrolytes. In several communications (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1556; 1926, 30, 1646; *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 225); from this laboratory we have shown that sols become less viscous on the addition of small quantities of electrolytes due to the increase of their electric charge by the adsorption of similarly charged ions. Hence the decrease of the viscosity of gelatin by the addition of neutral salts appears to be due to the adsorption of similarly charged ions.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) Positively charged gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture behaves abnormally towards dilution when coagulated by KCl , HCl and MgCl_2 and it could not be coagulated by BaCl_2 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$.

(2) The sol develops 'ionic antagonism' when coagulated by mixtures of KCl and K_2SO_4 , MgCl_2 and K_2SO_4 , HCl and K_2SO_4 , and HCl and KCl , and is markedly stabilised in presence of BaCl_2 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ when coagulated by KCl .

(3) The above sol shows positive acclimatization when coagulated by KCl , HCl and MgCl_2 .

(4) Negatively charged gelatin sol in alcohol-water mixture behaves abnormally towards dilution when coagulated by K_2SO_4 , $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and KOH and behaves normally towards dilution when coagulated by KCl.

(5) Negatively charged sol shows, no 'ionic antagonism' when coagulated by mixtures of KCl and K_2SO_4 , and 'ionic antagonism' is observed slightly when coagulated by mixtures of K_2SO_4 and $MgCl_2$. KOH stabilises the sol when it is coagulated by KCl.

(6) The phenomenon of positive acclimatization is observed with negatively charged sol when coagulated by K_2SO_4 and KOH, whilst marked negative acclimatization is developed when the sol is coagulated by HCl, $BaCl_2$, $MgCl_2$ and $Al(NO_3)_3$.

(7) Our results show that positively charged gelatin can adsorb cations and negatively charged gelatin, the anions, but gelatin adsorbs more of a cation than an anion. Similarly charged ions, therefore, play an important role in the coagulation of positively and negatively charged gelatin in alcohol-water mixture.

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